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ANALYSIS OF THE STRESS STATE OF A REINFORCED LAYER WITH TWO CYLINDRICAL CAVITIES AND SOME CONTACT-TYPE CONDITIONS

Abstract.

A spatial problem of elasticity theory is solved for a layer with two longitudinal cylindrical cavities and one longitudinal cylindrical inclusion under the given contact-type conditions on the lower surface of the layer. Stresses are specified on the other surfaces. Rigid conjugation conditions are taken into account between the layer and the inclusion. The solution to the problem is based on the Lamé equation, to which the generalized Fourier method is applied. A numerical analysis of the stress state of the layer is carried out and compared with the work where other boundary conditions are set.

Keywords: *layer with cylindrical cavities; generalized Fourier method; layer with cylindrical inclusions.*

Introduction. The analysis of the stress state of a body is the main area of deformable solid mechanics. The accuracy of calculations is the key to the efficient use of materials in the production of structures and mechanisms in the fields of mechanical and aircraft engineering. Therefore, it is important to choose the method that most accurately determines the stress-strain state of a body.

However, the complexity of the model often prevents the use of accurate (analytical) methods [1 – 4]. Thus, these classical works do not allow obtaining the stress-strain state for a body with more than three boundary surfaces. In this case, it is necessary to simplify the model or apply approximate (numerical) methods [5, 6]. However, using approximate methods does not always yield the required accuracy, especially for infinite elements.

An alternative is analytical and numerical methods, which have fewer limitations compared to analytical methods and high accuracy of the results obtained compared to numerical methods. But they are aimed at solving problems of their own, separate type. For example, works [7, 8] solve problems for a layer with a stress concentrator located perpendicular to the layer boundaries. This approach does not allow solving problems for a layer with longitudinal stress concentrators.

For problems with longitudinal stress concentrators, the generalized Fourier method is more suitable [9].

The generalized Fourier method has been used to solve problems for a cylinder with cylindrical cavities or inclusions [10 – 12]. However, these works do not take into account such an element as a layer.

The justification of the generalized Fourier method for a layer with a longitudinal stress concentrator is presented in [13]. Such a justification makes it possible to solve problems for a layer with a single cylindrical cavity or inclusion, presented in [14, 15], for a layer with several cavities or inclusions, presented in [16, 17].

The problem for a layer with two cylindrical cavities and one cylindrical inclusion was solved in [18, 19]. Thus, in [18], the boundary conditions are considered in the form of given displacements on the surfaces of the cavities (a layer on embedded supports), in [19], non-proprietary mixed boundary conditions on the upper and lower boundaries of the layer, and stresses on the surfaces of the cavities. However, these works do not allow solving the problem with contact-type conditions, which additionally requires the separation of the Lamé equation and the orthogonal transition formula.

Therefore, there is a need to create a method for solving a similar problem, taking into account the contact type conditions on the lower surface of the layer.

The purpose of the paper is to:

1. Solving a problem similar to [18, 19], but with contact-type conditions on the lower surface of the layer, and stresses on the upper surface and on the surfaces of the cavities.
2. Comparison of the results with [19] for analyzing the effect of contact-type boundary conditions instead of displacements on the stress state.

Problem statement. In an elastic homogeneous layer there are 2 circular cylindrical cavities and one cylindrical solid inclusion. The radius of inhomogeneities is denoted by R_p , where p is the number of cylinder, $p=1, 2, 3$.

The cylindrical heterogeneities were considered in local cylindrical coordinate systems (ρ_p, φ_p, z) , the layer in the Cartesian coordinate system (x, y, z) . The Cartesian coordinate system is equally oriented and combined

$y = -\tilde{h}$. Find the solution to the Lamé equation.

At the upper boundary of the layer, the stresses $F\vec{U}(x, z)|_{y=h} = \vec{F}_h^0(x, z)$, where

$$\vec{F}_h^0(x, z) = \tau_{yx}^{(h)}\vec{e}_x + \sigma_y^{(h)}\vec{e}_y + \tau_{yz}^{(h)}\vec{e}_z. \quad (1)$$

Contact type conditions are set at the lower boundary of the layer

$$U_y^{(0)}|_{y=-\tilde{h}} = U_y^{(\tilde{h})}, \quad (2)$$

$$\tau_{yx}^{(0)}|_{y=-\tilde{h}} = \tau_{yz}^{(0)}|_{y=-\tilde{h}} = 0, \quad (3)$$

where $U_y^{(\tilde{h})}$ are known functions.

On the surfaces of the cavities ($p = 2, 3$), the stresses $F\vec{U}(\varphi_p, z)|_{\rho_p=R_p} = \vec{F}_p^0(\varphi_p, z)$, where

$$\vec{F}_p^0(\varphi_p, z) = \sigma_\rho^{(p)}\vec{e}_\rho + \tau_{\rho\varphi}^{(p)}\vec{e}_\varphi + \tau_{\rho z}^{(p)}\vec{e}_z \quad (4)$$

are known functions.

Strict conjugation conditions apply between the layer and the inclusion

$$\vec{U}_0(\varphi, z)|_{\rho=R_1} = \vec{U}_p(\varphi, z)|_{\rho=R_1}, \quad (5)$$

$$F\vec{U}_0(\varphi, z)|_{\rho=R_1} = F\vec{U}_p(\varphi, z)|_{\rho=R_1}, \quad (6)$$

All given vectors and functions were assumed to decay rapidly to zero at far distances from the origin in the z -coordinate for cavity surfaces and in the x and z -coordinates for layer boundaries.

Research Methodology. The basic solutions of the Lamé equation are presented in the form [9].

$$\vec{u}_k^\pm(x, y, z; \lambda, \mu) = N_k^{(d)} e^{i(\lambda z + \mu x) \pm \gamma y};$$

$$\vec{R}_{k,m}(\rho, \varphi, z; \lambda) = N_k^{(p)} I_m(\lambda \rho) e^{i(\lambda z + m\varphi)}; \quad (7)$$

$$\vec{S}_{k,m}(\rho, \varphi, z; \lambda) = N_k^{(p)} \left[(\text{sign } \lambda)^m K_m(|\lambda| \rho) \cdot e^{i(\lambda z + m\varphi)} \right]; k = 1, 2, 3;$$

$$N_1^{(d)} = \frac{1}{\lambda} \nabla; N_2^{(d)} = \frac{4}{\lambda} (\nu - 1) \vec{e}_2^{(1)} + \frac{1}{\lambda} \nabla(y \cdot); N_3^{(d)} = \frac{i}{\lambda} \text{rot}(\vec{e}_3^{(1)} \cdot); N_1^{(p)} = \frac{1}{\lambda} \nabla;$$

$$N_2^{(p)} = \frac{1}{\lambda} \left[\nabla \left(\rho \frac{\partial}{\partial \rho} \right) + 4(\nu - 1) \left(\nabla - \vec{e}_3^{(2)} \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \right) \right]; N_3^{(p)} = \frac{i}{\lambda} \text{rot}(\vec{e}_3^{(2)} \cdot);$$

$$\gamma = \sqrt{\lambda^2 + \mu^2}, \quad -\infty < \lambda, \mu < \infty,$$

where ν is the Poisson's ratio; $I_m(x)$, $K_m(x)$ are modified Bessel functions; $\vec{R}_{k,m}$, $\vec{S}_{k,m}$, $k=1, 2, 3$ are internal and external solutions of the Lamé equation for a cylinder, respectively; $\vec{u}_k^{(-)}$, $\vec{u}_k^{(+)}$ are solutions of the Lamé equation for a layer.

The solution to the problem is presented in the form [19].

$$\begin{aligned} \vec{U}_0 = & \sum_{k=1}^3 \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \left(H_k(\lambda, \mu) \cdot \vec{u}_k^{(+)}(x, y, z; \lambda, \mu) + \tilde{H}_k(\lambda, \mu) \cdot \vec{u}_k^{(-)}(x, y, z; \lambda, \mu) \right) d\mu d\lambda + \\ & + \sum_{p=1}^3 \sum_{k=1}^3 \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-\infty}^{\infty} B_{k,m}^{(p)}(\lambda) \cdot \vec{S}_{k,m}(\rho_p, \varphi_p, z; \lambda) d\lambda, \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

$$\vec{U}_1 = \sum_{k=1}^3 \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-\infty}^{\infty} A_{k,m}(\lambda) \cdot \vec{R}_{k,m}(\rho_1, \varphi_1, z; \lambda) d\lambda, \quad (9)$$

where $\vec{S}_{k,m}(\rho_p, \varphi_p, z; \lambda)$, $\vec{u}_k^{(+)}(x, y, z; \lambda, \mu)$, $\vec{u}_k^{(-)}(x, y, z; \lambda, \mu)$ and $\vec{R}_{k,m}(\rho_1, \varphi_1, z; \lambda)$ are the basic solutions given by formulas (7), and the unknown functions $H_k(\lambda, \mu)$, $\vec{H}_k(\lambda, \mu)$, $B_{k,m}^{(p)}(\lambda)$ and $A_{k,m}(\lambda)$ must be found from the boundary conditions (1) – (4) and conjugation conditions (5), (6).

To find the unknowns (8) and (9), a system of integro-algebraic equations was created.

The first three equations are created when the boundary conditions at the upper boundary of the layer are met. To do this, the stress operator was applied to the right side of (8), and the known functions (1), previously represented by the double Fourier integral, were substituted into the left side of (8). With the help of transition functions [9], the basic solutions from the cylindrical coordinate system were rewritten into the Cartesian coordinate system.

Three more equations are written for contact-type conditions. In this case, the stress operator was applied to the right-hand side of (8), at \vec{e}_x and \vec{e}_z and the known functions (2), which were previously represented by the double Fourier integral, were substituted into the left-hand side of (8). The basic solutions were also written in a single Cartesian coordinate system.

To fulfill the boundary conditions on the surface of a cylindrical cavity p , the basis solutions of the right side of expression (8) are rewritten in stresses, and the given functions $\vec{F}_p^0(\varphi_p, z)$, which are represented by an integral and a Fourier series, are substituted into the left side. Using the transition functions [9], the basic solutions $\vec{u}_k^{\pm}(x, y, z; \lambda, \mu)$ and $\vec{S}_{k,m}(\rho_q, \varphi_q, z; \lambda)$, at $q \neq p$, are rewritten in the local cylindrical coordinate system of each cavity p . Thus, six more equations for the cavities are created.

Two additional equations are written as conjugation conditions (5), (6) between the layer and the inclusion ($p = 1$).

After getting rid of integrals and series, an infinite system of linear algebraic equations is obtained, which can be solved by the method of reduction. Thus, all unknown equations (3) were found.

Results and Discussion. Two longitudinal cylindrical cavities and one longitudinal cylindrical inclusion (steel, Poisson's ratio $\nu_0 = 0.38$, elastic modulus $E_0 = 1.7 \cdot 10^3$ MPa) are located in an elastic isotropic layer (plastic, Poisson's ratio $\nu_1 = 0.25$, elastic modulus $E_1 = 2 \cdot 10^5$ MPa).

Distance from the center of the inclusion to the upper and lower boundaries of the layer $h = \tilde{h} = 12$ mm. Radii of the cavity and inclusion $R_1 = R_2 = R_3 = 5$ mm. Distance from the inclusion to the cavities $p = 2$ and $p = 3$: $L_{12} = L_{13} = 30$ mm, $\alpha_{12} = 0$, $\alpha_{13} = \pi$.

At the upper boundary of the layer, the stresses $\sigma_y^{(h)}(x, z) = -10^8 \cdot (z^2 + 10^2)^{-2} \cdot (x^2 + 10^2)^{-2}$, $\tau_{yx}^{(h)} = \tau_{yz}^{(h)} = 0$ are set. Smooth contact conditions are set at the lower boundary of the layer $U_y^{(\tilde{h})} = 0$, $\tau_{yx}^{(0)}|_{y=-\tilde{h}} = \tau_{yz}^{(0)}|_{y=-\tilde{h}} = 0$. On the surfaces of the cavities, the stresses are given $\sigma_\rho^{(p)} = \tau_{\rho\varphi}^{(p)} = \tau_{\rho z}^{(p)} = 0$.

The infinite system was reduced to $m = 4$. The accuracy of the boundary conditions at the specified values of the geometric parameters is 10^{-4} .

To analyze the effect of contact-type conditions on the stress state in comparison with a rigid connection, the stress state data from [19] were used.

The stresses σ_ρ on the interface in the body of the layer are shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Stresses σ_ρ in the body of the layer at the interface ($p = 1$); 1 - under the specified contact type conditions; 2 - under the specified displacements.

As can be seen from Fig. 1, under the given contact-type conditions on the lower surface of the layer, the stresses σ_ρ increase. Moreover, zones of positive values appear.

The stresses of σ_φ on cylindrical surfaces $p = 1$ and $p = 2$ in comparison with [19] are shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Stresses σ_φ ; 1 - under the given conditions of contact type, surface $p = 1$; 2 - under the given displacements, surface $p = 1$; 3 - under the given conditions of contact type, surface $p = 2$; 4 - under the given displacements, surface $p = 2$.

The stresses σ_φ on the surface of the cavity $p = 1$ under the given contact-type conditions on the lower surface of the layer increase significantly, sometimes changing the sign to the opposite (Fig. 2, line 1).

On the surface of the second cavity, under the given contact-type conditions, on the contrary, the stresses σ_φ decrease, but their values almost coincide with those on the surface of the layer.

The stresses of σ_z on cylindrical surfaces $p = 1$ and $p = 2$ in comparison with [19] are shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Stresses σ_z ; 1 - under the given conditions of contact type, surface $p = 1$; 2 - under the given displacements, surface $p = 1$; 3 - under the given conditions of contact type, surface $p = 2$; 4 - under the given displacements, surface $p = 2$.

The stresses σ_z on the surfaces of the cavities $p = 1$ and $p = 2$ increase under the given contact-type conditions, while on the surface of $p = 1$ the sign sometimes changes to the opposite (Fig. 3, line 1).

Tangential stresses $\tau_{\rho\varphi}$ also differ from [19] and are shown in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4. Stresses $\tau_{\rho\varphi}$ on a cylindrical surface $p = 1$; 1 - under specified contact conditions; 2 - under specified displacements.

The tangential stresses $\tau_{\rho\varphi}$ on the body of the layer at the interface ($p = 1$) under the given contact-type conditions increase significantly compared to the case when the displacements are given (Fig. 4).

Conclusions. A method for solving the problem for a layer with two cylindrical cavities and one cylindrical inclusion under contact-type conditions at the lower boundary of the layer is proposed. The stress state in the places of stress concentration is obtained. A comparative analysis of the results with work [19], where displacements are specified instead of contact-type conditions, is carried out.

The comparative analysis shows significant changes in the stress state depending on these boundary conditions. Stresses decrease, increase, and change sign. Such changes in the stress state must be taken into account when designing for the loss of a rigid connection (delamination).

The method can be applied to structures whose design scheme coincides with the formulation of the given problem.

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